

The Unjournal

Evaluation 1 of "How Much Would Reducing Lead Exposure Improve Children's Learning in the Developing World?"

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This review aims to examine the relationship between blood lead levels and learning (including IQ as well as reading and mathematics). They find that reducing blood lead levels by one natural log unit increases cognitive outcomes by 0.12 standard deviations. Authors do a great job of explaining how data was harmonized to allow for comparison across studies, and in walking the reader through their analytical choices. They also do a nice job of situating their work in the context of other previous reviews. However, gold standard methodologies for conducting a systematic review are not utilized, and the potential biases that this introduces into the results are not acknowledged. There are also causal claims that cannot be supported by the type of data used in this case.

Major comments

Results are given as one natural log unit increase in blood lead is associated with X. It would be helpful to know, on average, what the differences are in average blood lead levels for children in LICs vis a vis MICs or HICs earlier in the intro (before you start getting into the results).

Phrases like 'causal link', 'causal interpretation' and 'effect of lead exposure' do not seem appropriate given the study designs. In other places, more appropriate phrasing like 'association' and 'relationship' are used. Phrasing should be tempered throughout the manuscript to reflect that this is not causal evidence. Despite arguing the causal link later in the manuscript, the data itself cannot make this claim, particularly when there are so many comorbidities to lead exposure that are also related to lower cognitive achievement (e.g., SES).

Authors need to acknowledge the search is not comprehensive. They state that they seek to identify "all studies measuring the correlation between blood levels and IQ or test scores", but then report that only existing SRs and Google Scholar were searched.

Please provide details on whether there were exclusions based on publication year or language.

On page 7, authors discuss that they include 286 estimates from 47 unique studies. It would be useful to know the minimum and maximum number of estimates contributed by a single study.

In Figures 3 and 4, please add the number of estimates being averaged for each study. It would also be useful to include the actual weighted average effect of the RVE model when referring to it in the Figure note. Finally, in Figure 4 there is a test of group differences presented (whether blood levels had a different effect of reading versus math?). It is unclear why this test was included or why such a difference would be expected. There is also no discussion of the test of group differences in text.

There needs to be a robust paragraph about the limitations of the systematic review methodology employed here. Gold standard SR methodology requires duplicate independent screening at full text to reduce bias. It also requires that risk of bias assessments are conducted in duplicate for each included study, and that results are

presented with reference to potential biases in the underlying literature. It should also acknowledge whether limitations were put on the publication year or language of the studies, and should acknowledge that the search was not comprehensive (e.g., no grey literature sources were mentioned).

Figure A3 should include the study citations. It is very surprising that Taylor (2017) would weaken the effect since it is a non-significant study without a particularly high weight. It would be great if the authors could confirm this is indeed the correct study.

A PRISMA flow chart should be included to illustrate each phase of the search process as well as the reasons for exclusion at full text.

It would be useful to have additional information in A1 and A2, e.g., sample size, age at lead testing, age at cognitive testing, what was the measure used for cognitive testing (for reading and math).

Minor comments

In the introduction, the second sentence of the first paragraph does not follow logically from the first. You state that 600 million children in L&MICs have elevated blood lead levels, and then you state that 3% of this comes from HIC (which are not even mentioned in the first sentence). Do you mean that 3% comes from middle-income countries?

I am not sure who the target audience is, but when sigma is first used in the text (on page one of the intro) it may be useful to explain that this is the symbol for standard deviation.

On p. 31, in the first full sentence, please add the unit of measurement for the 149 and 15 numbers.

Editorial comments

Avoid the use of contractions. For example, P. 22 – change don't to do not in several places. On p. 31, change doesn't to does not.

P. 23 – change instructional to instrumental.

P. 30, Section 5.2.1, the authors name at the end of the first sentence should be inside of the parentheses.